

CURRENT INDICATIONS AND METHODS OF PERIODONTAL SPLINTING

Stakhanska O.O.

PhD, MD, Associate Professor
ORCID: 0000-0003-3013-1346

Patskan L.O.

PhD, MD, Associate Professor
ORCID: 0000-0003-2584-5942

Pohoretska K.V.

PhD, MD, Associate Professor
ORCID: 0000-0002-6505-6086

I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University
Maidan Voli 1, 46000, Ternopil, Ukraine

***Abstract.** Periodontitis is a microbially associated, host-mediated inflammatory disease. Its primary features include the loss of periodontal attachment and marginal alveolar bone loss. Progressive alveolar bone loss eventually leads to hypermobility of his teeth, which has a negative impact on masticatory function or chewing comfort, aesthetics, and phonetics.*

The treatment of the periodontitis usually involves nonsurgical and surgical periodontal treatments but sometimes may be limited to only the nonsurgical periodontal treatment.

The treatment of periodontitis-associated tooth mobility may involve specific treatment for the different stages of periodontitis starting from simple occlusal therapy, splinting, non-surgical phase therapy till surgical phase therapy.

This article discusses the overview of classifications, objectives, indication, contraindication, principles and various materials used for splinting.

Splinting is a procedure by which a tooth resistance to an applied force, is increased by joining it, to a neighboring tooth or teeth, is a well-accepted clinical treatment used to control irreversible tooth mobility through mechanical stabilization.

Splinting appears to be the rational safety procedure to employ when a tooth must withstand forces beyond its individual physiologic limit. By splinting, the pathologic tilting of the individual tooth is transformed into a physiologic bodily movement analogous to the bodily movements of the roots of multirooted teeth.

Splinting plays dual role both as primary therapeutic measure as well as adjuvant in stabilizing the teeth for future surgical therapy, saves a significant number of mobile teeth but requires a high degree of clinical skill and diagnostic expertise.

Splinting is considered an important component of a periodontal treatment plan because of its ability to provide coaptive stability to the teeth and greatly improve the outcome and prognosis of teeth affected by periodontal disease.

Keywords: *Splinting, Periodontitis, mobility, stabilization.*

Introduction

Periodontitis is the inflammatory disease of periodontium progressing to destruction of soft & hard tissue in the oral cavity. It is caused by certain bacteria and by local factors progressing from gingivitis to periodontitis and leading to the morbidity and loss of the tooth [1].

Loss of tooth-supporting structures results in tooth mobility. Increased tooth mobility adversely affects function, aesthetics, and the patient's comfort. Splints are used to over-come all these problems. When faced with the dilemma of how to manage periodontally compromised teeth, splinting of mobile teeth to stronger adjacent teeth is a viable option. This prolongs the life expectancy of loose teeth,

gives stability for the periodontium to reattach, and improves comfort, function and aesthetics. Although splinting has been used since ancient times, it has been a topic of controversy because of its ill effects on oral health, including poor oral hygiene and adverse effects on supporting teeth [2].

There have been considerable advancements in the materials used for splinting, resulting in fewer ill effects. This article is intended to provide the clinicians with an updated overview of splinting, types and classification of splints, with their indications, contraindications, rationale and effects on oral health [3].

Definition

Splint: A splint is any device which joins two or more teeth in order to provide support and to reduce mobility. According to Glossary of Periodontics Term 1986 a splint is “an appliance designed to stabilize a mobile tooth”.

According to AAP (1996) a splint has been defined “as an apparatus, appliance, or device employed to prevent motion or displacement of fractured or mobile parts”.

The Glossary of Prosthodontic Term defines a splint “as a rigid or flexible device that maintains in position a displaced or movable part; also used to keep in place & protect the injured part” [4].

Classification of splints

There are many techniques for splinting teeth.

I. According to duration:

✓ Temporary or provisional:

- They are used to assist healing after injury or after surgical treatment.

- Are placed for less than 2 months.

- They should be reasonably easy to apply to mobile teeth and also easy to remove after healing has taken place.

- Examples are composite resin splint on acid etched surface with no tooth preparation, wire and acrylic splint, orthodontic bands, acrylic bite-guards.

✓ Semi-permanent:

- They are placed for months to years
- May be employed during an observational period before determination of the long-term prognosis.

- Examples are: composite resin splint with tooth preparation in the anterior region, removable cast chrome-cobalt alloy frameworks incorporating finger clasps for retention, wire placed in continuous posterior MODs amalgams and subsequently filled with composite resins

- ✓ Permanent/Definitive:

- They are placed for the life of the teeth.
- It is employed during complex oral rehabilitation where abutments are highly mobile or where a few abutments must support the entire prosthesis.

- Examples are fixed splints like inlays or crowns and removable splints like chrome-cobalt partial denture with extensions covering the lingual surfaces of the teeth to be protected.

II. According to design:

- ✓ Removable: It can be removed by the patient.
- ✓ Fixed: It cannot be removed by the patient. Fixed prosthesis works as a permanent splint

III. According to fabrication technique:

- ✓ Direct: fabricated inside the mouth.
- ✓ Indirect: fabricated outside the mouth in the lab.

IV. According to tooth preparation:

- ✓ Intracoronal: where the splint takes retention form inside the crown, with cavity preparation.

- ✓ Extracoronal: where the splint takes, retention form the external surface of crown. e.g Ligature wire, night guards. etc. [5, 6]

Rationale for Splinting

- Rest: As for many injured or diseased parts of the body, immobilization, permits undisturbed healing.

- Redistribution of Forces: The stabilization of weakend teeth by splinting increases resistance to applied force. Reciprocal antagonisms that increases the effective root area are provided.

- Redirection of Forces: Splinting effects a redirection of force in a more axial direction over all the included in a splint.

- Preservation Of arch Integrity: Splinting restores, proximal contacts that have been disrupted by missing and migrated teeth, makes the patient more comfortable, and reduces the likelihood of food impaction and consequent break down.

- Restoration of arch stability: splinting restores proximal contacts, that have been disrupted by missing and migrated teeth, that makes the patient more comfortable, and reduces the liklihood of food impaction and cosequent break down.

- Psychologic well-being: Hypermobility can become so severe that patients become fearful of losing teeth. Stabilization by splinting and restoration not only improves function, but it also can restore a sense of a well being [3].

Indications for splinting:

- restore patients' masticatory function and comfort;
- stabilize teeth with increasing mobility that have not responded to occlusal adjustment and periodontal treatment;
- facilitate periodontal instrumentation and occlusal adjustment of extremely mobile teeth;
- prevent tipping or drifting of teeth and extrusion of unopposed teeth;
- stabilize teeth, when indicated, following orthodontic movement;
- create adequate occlusal stability when replacing missing teeth;
- stabilize teeth following acute trauma [7, 8].

Contraindications:

- moderate to severe tooth mobility in the presence of periodontal inflammation and/or primary occlusal trauma.
- insufficient number of firm/ sufficiently firm teeth to stabilize mobile teeth;

- prior occlusal adjustment has not been done on teeth with occlusal trauma or occlusal interferences.

- patient not maintaining oral hygiene.

- when the sole objective of splinting is to decrease tooth mobility following the removal of the splint [9].

Splint used in periodontally compromised dentition.

Composite resin splints. Restorative materials that are polymerized by ultraviolet light are very useful in providing stabilization of excessively mobile teeth. Basically, the technique is a simple one and provides adequate stabilization if care is taken during the actual operative procedures [10, 11]

Wire ligation is the most commonly used type of stabilization. Wire used is 0.008” stainless steel. It is easy to construct. However, one of its basic limitations is that it can be utilized only where coronal form permits; Because of this shortcoming it has its greatest use in stabilizing the mandibular incisors [12, 13].

Fibre Reinforced Materials. Fibre splints use a polyethylene or kevlar fibre mesh and are attached either with an unfilled resin such as and/or with composite resin. Materials such as fiber-splint (polydentia samezzovico-vira, Switzerland), ribbondtm (ribbond inc., seattle, usa) or everstick (stick tech ltd, Turku, Finland), which is a silinated e-type glass fibre, are commercially available [14].

Figure 1. Materials used for teeth splinting

Figure 2. Splinting in periodontal treatment plan

Conclusion. Clinical relevance: Used correctly, periodontal splinting can greatly improve the comfort, prognosis and outcome for a patient with serious periodontal disease. But used incorrectly, splinting can cause further deterioration in periodontal health.

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